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УДК 330.46:519.86

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Methodology for managing compensatory financing of infrastructure projects in the post-war recovering of Ukraine

The subject of the study is a set of theoretical, scientific and practical provisions for the formation of methodology for managing compensatory financing of infrastructure projects in post-war recovery of Ukraine.

The purpose of the study is to develop a methodology for managing compensatory financing of infrastructure projects in post-war recovery of Ukraine.

Research methods. In order to comply with the conceptual integrity of scientific development, the dialectical method of scientific cognition, as well as empirical-theoretical and formal-logical principles were used.

Results of work. The conducted theoretical analysis provided an opportunity to highlight the specifics of compensatory financing of infrastructure projects in terms of modern concepts. According to the results of the research, the structural components of the management methodology of compensatory financing of infrastructure projects of post-war reconstruction are proposed, in particular, the mechanism of its implementation is presented.

Field of application of results. The presented developments should be implemented in the work of enterprises, namely in the implementation of infrastructure projects, taking into account the specifics of modern concepts of compensatory financing management.

Conclusions. The possibility of attracting additional financial resources to development of infrastructure projects through the technology of compensatory financing based on deferred tax payments (Tax Increment Financing – TIF) was studied. Based on the results of the study, proposals are presented on the formation of an investment mechanism for enterprises – institutional stakeholders of the infrastructure projects based on the principles of the TIF, using the structure, levers, tools, methods of financing measures. The coordination center of the infrastructure projects has been determined and the stakeholders of this integration formation have been proposed.

Key words: management, compensatory financing, infrastructure projects, methodology, functions, post-war recovery.

КЛИМЧУК М.М.
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Методологія управління компенсаторним фінансуванням інфраструктурних проєктів в пост-воєнному відновленні України

Предметом дослідження є сукупність теоретичних, науково-практичних положень щодо формування методології управління компенсаторним фінансуванням інфраструктурних проєктів в пост-воєнному відновленні України.

Метою дослідження є формування методології управління компенсаторним фінансуванням інфраструктурних проєктів у пост-воєнному відновленні України.

Методи дослідження. З метою дотримання концептуальної цілісності наукової розробки використано діалектичний метод наукового пізнання, а також емпірико-теоретичний та формально-логічний принципи.

Результати роботи. Проведений теоретичний аналіз надав можливість виокремити специфіку компенсаторного фінансування інфраструктурних проєктів в розрізі сучасних концепцій. За результатами проведеного дослідження запропоновано структурні компоненти методології управління компенсаторним фінансуванням інфраструктурних проєктів пост-воєнного відновлення, зокрема представлено механізм її реалізації.

Галузь застосування результатів. Представлені розробки доцільно імплементувати в роботу підприємств, а саме при реалізації інфраструктурних проєктів з урахуванням специфіки сучасних концепцій управління компенсаторним фінансуванням.

Висновки. Досліджено можливість залучення додаткових фінансових ресурсів у розвиток інфраструктурних проєктів за допомогою технології компенсаторного фінансування на основі відстрочених податкових платежів (Tax Increment Financing – TIF). За результатами дослідження подано пропозиції щодо формування інвестиційного механізму для підприємств – інституційних стейкхолдерів інфраструктурних проєктів на основі принципів TIF із використанням структури, важелів, інструментів, методів фінансування заходів. Визначено координаційний центр інфраструктурних проєктів та запропоновано стейкхолдерів цього інтеграційного утворення.

Ключові слова: управління, компенсаторне фінансування, інфраструктурні проєкти, методологія, функції, пост-воєнне відновлення.

Introduction. The European economy is undergoing unprecedented transformations towards a fair green and digital future in a context of massive uncertainties linked to the global and security outlook. Since spring 2021, the economy has seen a strong economic rebound from the COVID-19

pandemic. The output levels have fully recovered, also thanks to the exceptional support measures taken at EU and national levels. The pandemic and the EU policy response have accelerated the twin transition of the EU economy and highlighted the need to strengthen the resilience of the EU economy [10].

On 18 May 2022, the European Commission issued a communication as regards its plans of Ukraine's relief and reconstruction. The document recognises that international support for Ukraine, especially by the EU, must concern both the support during the war and efforts to rebuild the country after the war. In this vein, the European Commission will propose new macro-financial assistance in 2022 to cover EUR 9 bln out of the EUR 14.3 bln financing gap (according to IMF estimates). Yet, the reconstruction of Ukraine would require much more significant resources. The European Commission envisages that the strategic reconstruction plan will be developed by the recently organised National Council for Reconstruction while its implementation will be geared by the RebuildUkraine reconstruction platform to be created with the participation of Ukraine, EU and other international donors. This platform would in particular ensure sound management of the funds. Importantly, Ukraine's reconstruction will be integrated with the EU integration process and will take into account the requirements of EU's green and digital agendas [11].

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. This issue updates the study of using the Tax Increment Financing (TIF) mechanism in financing of post-war recovering of Ukraine [5; 9]. Thus, D. Huddleston describes the application of the TIF method to the Wisconsin example, with an emphasis on the change in the structure of taxes received additionally from other budget [1, p. 11–17].

Authors in their study made efforts to identify the circumstances when the TIF project would be an effective means of developing municipal economies [6, p. 123]. T. Stinson and D. Huddleston calculated the financial sustainability of certain projects, based on the expected growth rates of property value [8, p. 241–248]. J. Klemanski, along with financial aspects, assessed the effects of TIF in the political and legal field [2, p. 23–28]. J. Mean and M. Rosentraub analyzed the relationship between the increase in the property value and the application of TIF [7, p. 23–26].

The author notes that, among urban planners, tax increment financing (TIF) is a popular economic development financing tool. Using eighteen years of TIF district-level data, this study finds that TIF was most likely a fiscal boon for districts [6].

How to notice scientist B. Schneider the compensatory technology of «Tax Increment Financing» is

a powerful and controversial force in American urbanism. Every state except Arizona currently allows it, as does the District of Columbia, and it has become the most popular incentive tool for economic development in the United States as the federal government has decreased its urban development spending. TIF plays a role in megaprojects such as Chicago's Lincoln Yards and Amazon's HQ2 in Arlington, Virginia, as well as in smaller-scale neighborhood improvements, affordable housing, and transit projects. With its application in vastly different contexts across nearly every state, TIF is used to fund a broad range of projects. Currently, the method is most popular in post-industrial, Rust Belt cities and towns [4].

The purpose of the article is to develop a methodology for managing compensatory financing of infrastructure projects in post-war recovery of Ukraine.

Results of the research. With hostilities taking place across the whole country, the economic situation has deteriorated rapidly. GDP is expected to fall by 30 to 50 % this year and tax revenues dropped by around 50 to 80%. The estimated overall damage runs already in the hundreds of billions of euros, with more than EUR 100 billion in damage to physical infrastructure alone [11].

Now more than ever, the Union should leverage its international partnerships to join forces on common challenges and promote peace and stability, as well as a rule-based international order and effective multilateralism. The coordinated response by the Union and its international partners to the invasion of Ukraine shows how the Union can work to achieve those objectives. At the same time, new sources of risks and uncertainty have emerged and need to be addressed. While most companies and supply chains showed a high degree of resilience and adaptability during the pandemic, the recovery and the recent developments linked to Ukraine's invasion have revealed a number of vulnerabilities, including in the energy sector, which must be tackled to protect our European way of life, maintain growth and improve resilience in the longer run. The events of the past few weeks and the rapidly worsening geopolitical context should not divert our focus. Instead, they confirm the need to accelerate the ongoing economic transformation [10–11].

The reconstruction effort will need to build on Ukraine's ownership, close cooperation and co-

ordination with supporting countries and organisations, and Ukraine's strategic partnership with the Union. Reconstruction will also require mobilising resources at regional and local level. Peer-to-peer cooperation and programmes embedded in partnerships between cities and regions in the European Union and those in Ukraine will enrich and accelerate reconstruction.

Four major pillars of reconstruction can already be envisaged:

- Rebuilding the country, in particular infrastructure, health services, housing and schools, as well as digital and energy resilience in line with the most recent European policies and standards;
- Continue modernising the state and its institutions to ensure good governance and respect for the rule of law, by providing administrative capacity support and technical assistance, including at regional and local level;
- Implementing a structural and regulatory agenda with the aim of deepening the economic and societal integration of Ukraine and its people with the EU in line with its European path;
- Support the recovery of Ukraine's economy and society by promoting sustainable and inclusive economic competitiveness, sustainable trade, and private sector development, while contributing to the green and digital transition of the country [11].

Tax Increment Financing (TIF) creates special tax districts around targeted redevelopment areas from which future tax revenues are diverted to finance infrastructure improvements and/or development. At the beginning of the TIF period, tax revenues in the TIF district going to general city services are frozen at a certain rate. All additional tax revenues go toward directly funding new development or servicing debts related to new development until the end of the TIF period, which usually lasts 20 to 30 years. Supporters say the new tax revenues generated by TIFs would not have taken place «but for» the investment that the TIF enabled, and that they are a valuable tool for neighborhood revitalization [4].

TIF is aimed to provide the investor with compensation through special funds replenished by tax revenues from incomes which were obtained after construction and putting into operation the infrastructure objects. The basis of this mechanism is redevelopment, financed by an investor who invests in construction and reimburses his expenses

from the special fund, accumulating taxes paid by the owners of new consolidated facilities.

That is, TIF is a mechanism covering the investor's expenses into implementation of infrastructure projects from the budget by tax revenues from incomes which were obtained after construction and putting into operation the infrastructure objects. In fact, this is one of the variants to apply compensatory tax models for investment purposes across the regions. After all, the TIF envisages that the investor's costs put into the investment project will be compensated by a tax exemption calculated in the future.

We suggest to introduce the mechanism of TIF in development of infrastructure projects in the post-war recovery of Ukraine, since has become the most popular form of manufacturing and commercial activity, which is they by trends and challenges in the real sector of the economy. We believe that globalization and the potential symbiosis associated with it are an expression of the benefits and opportunities that can be gained as a result of the joining forces and the competitive advantages of collaborating actors.

In the suggested mechanism, the methods of financing are identified. Methods and techniques that help to substantiate and control specific management decisions related to the search for financing, their rational structure and use of financial compensatory technology based on deferred tax payments (Tax Increment Financing – TIF).

Let us identify the benefits of financing TIF-based projects: the distribution of risks between the stakeholders; protection against default of other assets and against increase in financial and credit obligations of project owners; growth of the leverage ratio, that is, the ratio of the company's borrowed capital to its own funds, which leads to an increase in the return on equity capital and a decrease in its value in total capital.

The basic mechanism for realizing the risk of deferred payment includes:

- low level of motivation of private investors to finance infrastructure projects at their own expense;
- withdrawal of private investors' capital from economic circulation, which leads to losses and the impossibility of making a profit;
- an increase in the cost of borrowed resources for investment, which is due to market conditions and inflationary processes;

– low quality of income forecasting from the implementation of the infrastructure project, as a result, the uncertainty of the project payback parameters.

Potentially, these risks can lead to an increase in the return period for investment in an infrastructure project, as well as to a change in the current tax conditions, which will reduce the return on investment. In this regard, stability is an important condition for the success of the mechanism of state tax policy, which improves the quality of forecasting. The most commonly used TIF bonds provide additional profits for the TIF zone. For three years, when tax revenues in the TIF are insufficient, the interest on such bonds is usually capitalized. When income stabilization is achieved, interest is paid and the principal is serviced.

The attractiveness of this financing scheme for local authorities lies in the fact that investors take on the risks of implementing the project and receiving income in a sufficient amount and with a certain frequency of income. And TIF bonds are not assigned a rating, which makes them more profitable, but at the same time more risky financial assets.

If it is not possible to place bonds on the market at the initial stage of the implementation of an infrastructure project (for example, private investors do not want to buy bonds, the nominal amount of financing is lower than required, etc.), a distribution (pay-as-you-go) mechanism is used, which can be financed through reconstruction or modernization programs within TIF zones or by issuing securities, including bills of exchange. In some cases, bonds may be issued for amounts in excess of the amount owed. The reason for this exemption is the expectation of income from tax payments in connection with the commissioning of the new infrastructure.

In our opinion, the introduction of foreign practices in the implementation of TIF-based projects in the Ukrainian realities requires some adaptation processes that consider the issues of finding sources of financing, including the interest of private investors in long-term capital investment, the risks of using the mechanism of deferred tax payments, as well as the weakness of the financial base in most regions. International models of financing infrastructure projects and insurance of risks used in international practice must be adapted to the specifics of the development formats of our economy.

Conclusions

The overall reconstruction of Ukraine will require comprehensive support to rebuild the country after the war damage, to create the foundations of a free and prosperous country, anchored in European values, well integrated into the European and global economy, and to support it on its European path [11].

The conducted theoretical analysis provided an opportunity to highlight the specifics of compensatory financing of infrastructure projects in terms of modern concepts. According to the results of the research, the structural components of the management methodology of compensatory financing of infrastructure projects of post-war reconstruction are proposed, in particular, the mechanism of its implementation is presented.

The possibility of attracting additional financial resources to development of infrastructure projects through the technology of compensatory financing based on deferred tax payments (Tax Increment Financing – TIF) was studied.

Based on the results of the study, proposals are presented on the formation of an investment mechanism for enterprises – institutional stakeholders of the infrastructure projects based on the principles of the TIF, using the structure, levers, tools, methods of financing measures. The coordination center of the infrastructure projects has been determined and the stakeholders of this integration formation have been proposed.

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ЗОРИНА О.А.

Податкові та митні преференції під час воєнного стану: вплив змін у законодавстві на діяльність суб'єктів малого бізнесу

Актуальність теми дослідження. Після початку повномасштабного вторгнення росії в Україну багато підприємств та фізичних осіб – підприємців, що опинилися в зоні бойових дій, припинили свою роботу або були вимушені евакуюватися в інші більш безпечні області України чи за кордон, у зв'язку з чим усі представники бізнесу стикаються з труднощами. Окрім того, війна росії проти України зумовила різку необхідність у тому, аби спростити митне оформлення різних груп товарів, вкрай необхідних як для забезпечення Збройних сил України додатковим захисним та військовим спорядженням, так і для забезпечення цивільних їжею, ліками та іншими товарами першої необхідності. За час дій правового режиму воєнного стану було прийнято низку нових законів щодо внесення змін до податкового законодавства.

Метою дослідження є: аналіз змін у нормативно-правовому регулюванні щодо підтримки малого бізнесу та пільгового оподаткування імпорту під час війни та формування пропозицій щодо його вдосконалення.